

COREnect initial Roadmap ideas

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As a result of internal workshops held in November 2020 within the three Expert Groups Computing/Storage, Communication/Sensing and Peripheral, consortium-internal and external experts from industry, research institutes, universities, and European associations aligned their views on Europe's major challenges and opportunities. Combining their specialist knowledge, COREnect benefits from broad insights into crucial fields that require our attention and thus, be able to address the upcoming challenges in Europe regarding 5G and beyond. Altogether, capturing and crystallizing the discussions, the three Expert Groups will cooperatively develop the COREnect industry roadmap in the first half-year of 2021.

As the initial idea for the COREnect industry roadmap, Expert Group 1 (EG1) identifies open challenges for innovations in the area of digital computing chips that would ensure European technological sovereignty. Since controlling every component may not be realistic, the focus lies on keeping checks and balances. As an initial result, the EG identified challenges regarding KPIs, instruction set architecture, storage, multiprocessor system on a chip, operating systems, and system architecture.

Expert Group 2 (EG2) investigates how Europe can establish leadership and sovereignty in the field of communications and sensing. This domain is subject to an insatiable demand of ever-increasing data rates, leading to ever-growing challenges on the technological side. Within EG2, the main focus is set on data center infrastructure for cloud-centric applications, wireless infrastructure, industrial-grade connectivity, and consumer-grade connectivity. Initial outputs are gap analyses for each focus area, e.g., covering hardware design in very advanced CMOS, availability of and access to advanced CMOS processes, and silicon photonics technologies. Further, the aspect of sovereignty on CAD software is highlighted next to non-technical gaps that hinder advancements on the telecommunication side.

Expert Group 3 (EG3) will contribute with a focus on supplementary core technologies that support the design of computing components (EG1) and communication technologies (EG2). As essentials for controlling the telecommunication and vertical value chain, the Peripheral technologies were scrutinized, with crucial challenges identified and further investigated as initial results. Technology and application requirements, as well as access to manufacturing and strategic choices of Europe in the value chain were considered, resulting in the three focus areas: core process technologies for addressing the needs of Europe, system and component architectures as well as power management and energy efficiency on device and system level.

With continuous exchange internally and between the Expert Groups, the industry roadmap will develop a holistic approach by examining electronics for reliable communication, future core-technologies, integration, and energy-efficient communication electronics from different viewpoints. Thus, the initial COREnect industry roadmap will build synergies and paves the way towards Europe's strongholds and opportunities.